

**Succession Planning in Family Businesses in Jordan: Problems,
Causes, Consequences and Remedies**

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Submission Statement

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Succession Planning in SMEs and Family Businesses in Jordan: Problems, Causes,
Consequences and Remedies

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We hereby certify that this Dissertation submitted by Furat Jabr conforms to acceptable standards, and as such is fully adequate in scope and quality. It is therefore approved as the fulfillment of the Dissertation requirements for the degree of Masters in international management.

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Certification Statement

I hereby certify that this paper constitutes my own product, that where the language of others is set forth, quotation marks so indicate, and that appropriate credit is given where I have used the language, ideas, expressions or writings of another.

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Abstract

This study investigates the succession processes in family businesses in Jordan, the problems faced, causes of these problems and the consequences. The study suggests remedies for the succession problem to ensure the survival of family businesses in Jordan.

This research also highlights the importance of corporate governance and suggests that it improves the performance, growth and management efficiency of family businesses. The research suggests that the adoption of corporate governance into the local family businesses will ensure the success and succession of generations.

The research tackles the issue of cultural constraints in Jordan that affect the selection process such as the adhering to the masculine management stereotypes and the perception of family business success is effected by gender.

The study uses a sample of 8 local family businesses and interviewed both the founders and successors. Findings revealed that the lack of succession planning, corporate governance, proper educational background and board of directors were the main problems in the face of family businesses.

It is recommended that family businesses make succession process an ongoing event and not deal with it as a one-time event that is usually dealt with in Jordan in the case of death or illness of the founder.

Keywords: family business, succession planning, corporate governance, resistance to change

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Chapter 1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter gives an overview on the literature that has been formulated on succession in family owned businesses so as to form a foundation the theoretical framework that is used to achieve the research objectives and come to conclusions on the problems, causes, consequences and remedies of succession in family businesses in Jordan.

1.1 Introduction

Today's economic and political climate in the middle east makes it more important than ever for family owned businesses and SMEs in Jordan to put into practice effective planning and corporate governance frameworks so to guarantee the success of their businesses and the perpetuation of the wealth of the family across generations.

The vast majority of businesses in the Middle East are owned and controlled by families; an estimate of 75-90 percent of businesses in the Middle East are family owned (Alderso 2010). Mainly, family owned SMEs are the backbone of developing economies and so their sustainability is very important to Jordan's economic growth.

But the most common situation for local family owned SMEs in Jordan is that many have closed down or split up into smaller companies once it reached to the third generation.

An interesting characteristic of family owned businesses is their light use of bureaucracy which gives them an aspect of flexibility in solving business problems. They do not need elaborate decision making methods because of their informality and intimacy. On the

other hand, family owned businesses are not aware of how the growth of the business is changing them. The irony here is that the self-same characteristic that gives family owned SMEs competitive advantage also contributes to the destructive conflict that could happen to the business. The lack of formal rules and systems facilitate easy and quick decision making but it can also be an obstacle to the introduction of good corporate governance. (Jordaan 2012)

In the 2nd Family Business Conference held in Amman it was stated in their report that there is an alarming rate of collapse among family owned businesses in the Middle East. Despite the size of the business, family owned businesses face important challenges that puts their performance at risk and endangers their survival. Such challenges include management and succession planning, management of wealth, employment of family and non family executives, creating correct governance structure, etc. Family businesses in Jordan contribute largely to the growth and employment in the economy. However, family businesses face challenges that are serious enough to threaten their survival and sustainability. The life span of family businesses in the Arab world is 24 years. Only 30% pass it on to the second generation, and only 10% pass it on to the third generation and after that only 3% survive past the third generation. (FBC, 2010)

Many Jordanian family companies are small businesses but despite the fail rate, several Jordanian family businesses have become multinationals such as Nuqul Group who started in 1952 as a small trading company but has regionally expanded with almost 5100 employee spanning several continents. (nuqulgroup.com, 2012) such examples show that family businesses can have a sustainable competitive advantage.

That is why it is important to see what family businesses are doing right and what are they doing wrong in their practices. Family businesses have their own unique and complex issues such as family member rivalry and the succession of generations. And so by being aware of these challenges and developing strategies that can insure the continuity of businesses, Jordan's economic performance and development will be positively affected through the increased GDP and exports.

Corporate governance will also limit the conflicts that could happen internally and ensure a smooth transition of ownership to heirs. Abou-el-fatouh (2009) states that "Corporate governance framework ensures that shareholders are freed from executive and administrative duties. As a result, conflicts among business owners who assume management roles in the organization would be reduced to a greater extent particularly in organizations owned by a few number of shareholders where the distinction between ownership and management capacity is blurred".

In general, the adoption of a corporate awareness framework is not common in Jordan or even in the Middle East for that matter. This is because of the misconception that adopting corporate governance requires high costs with no guarantees that these costs will generate benefits to the family business.(Abou-el-fatouh H, 2009) This study delves into the considerations needed to reduce the problems that could arise from implementing the corporate governance (such as inexpensive financial alternatives).

Despite all that and before diagnosing the succession in family owned businesses in Jordan, there is more to be considered. As stated Lansberg (1988), family dynamics need to be considered.

Accordingly, Whatley L (2011) created a new model that combines two other existing models. This research uses this new model for family owned business succession that considers the family dynamics.

1.2 Research Aims, Objectives and Research Questions

The title of this research study is “Succession planning in SMEs and family businesses in Jordan: Problems, causes, consequences and remedies”.

This research study examines the importance of corporate governance for family owned businesses and how it improves performance, growth and management efficiency. The challenges of family owned businesses are addressed in this research along with recommendations on facing such challenges. The research includes investigation on how corporate governance can be incorporated into local family owned businesses in Jordan to ensure the success and succession of generation.

This research provides possible suggestions to family owned businesses that can be adopted and implemented so to ensure a successful transfer from one generation to the next in Jordan.

This research, unlike any other, tackles the issue of cultural constraints in Jordan that affect the selection of successors. Wasta and family obligations are a few of these

constraints that hinder the process of selecting a good successor and leader of a family business.

The research aims of the dissertation are therefore to:

- To identify succession strategies of the first generation of Jordanian entrepreneurs.
- To highlight the importance of sound governance practices to assist local Jordanian SMEs deal with growth and success.
- To investigate succession issues within local family owned businesses and show the complexity in having competent family leadership across the family generations.
- To research ways to overcome resistance to change resulting from the transition of family owned businesses to ones that practice corporate governance.

1.3 Dissertation Synopsis

This research is organized according to the following structure:

Chapter 2 reviews the literature on family businesses. It starts off with the different definitions in literature on family businesses. However, all these different definitions have common characteristics of family businesses. Then, the chapter goes through the unique characteristics of family businesses that give them competitive advantages over their non family-owned counterparts. However despite the unique characteristics, the literature reveals some challenges to the continuity of family businesses. The chapter

then moves on to the definition of succession and succession planning. The literature review shows highlights the importance of succession management to family owned businesses. The chapter also discusses the resistance in family businesses to succession planning that could hinder their succession process. The reasons behind their resistance are also discussed. In this chapter, the nature of the succession process is reviewed so to help the author come to a concluding framework for Jordanian family businesses that could help them in their continuity. Also, the successor selection process, as well as the preparation and mentoring process of successors is discussed. The chapter then reviews the importance of corporate governance to the succession of family businesses. Finally, a review of the theoretical models on succession and family performance is displayed in this chapter to help figure out the relation between succession and the businesses' performance.

Chapter 3 describes the methodology, research design, and analysis strategy of this research. Moreover, the chapter discusses the methods for guaranteeing the validity and reliability of the study.

Chapter 4 discusses the research results and shows how these results correlate to the existing literature. Also, the chapter provides answers to the research questions in the form of a set of guidelines and implications for family owned businesses in Jordan.

Chapter 5 summarizes the research results and gives answers to the research questions. This chapter also goes through the weaknesses and potential future research projects of the study.

Chapter 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter critically reviews the academic literature on family succession planning and problems. It is important to understand the theoretical underpinnings and the existing knowledge of the topic to frame and analyze the questions of the dissertation.

This chapter presents a literature review on the following key concepts of this study: the definition of family business, the unique characteristics of family business, the challenges to the continuity of family business, the definition of succession and succession plan, the importance of succession, resistance to succession planning, the succession process, the selection of a successor, and the preparation of successors and mentoring.

The purpose of this research is to review the problems, causes, and consequences of succession planning in family owned businesses in Jordan. At the end of this study, there will be suggested remedies for these challenges and consequences. This research will fill the gap in literature that does not go deep into the cultural obligations of Jordan in terms of family relations and business.

2.1 Definition of Family Business

An exact definition of a family business still remains to this day a topic of argument as there are several definitions reported in the literature despite the progress within the field of research. Neubauer and Lank (1998) have done a detailed but not

comprehensive review of several definitions of a family business shown in the table below:

Barry (1975)	A family business is one which in practice, is controlled by only one family.
Bork (1986)	A family business is that which has been founded by a member of the family and has been passed on, or is expected to be passed on, to family descendents. The descendents of the original founder or founders will own and control the business. Furthermore, they will work and participate in the business and members of the family will profit from that business.
Carsurd (1992)	The family business is one in which ownership and the decision-making process are dominated by members of a group in which affinity is based on affection.
Gallo and Sveen (1991)	A business in which only one family owns the majority of the capital and has overall control. Members of the family form part of management and take the most important decisions.
Handler (1989)	An organization in which the main operative decisions and plans for succession within the management are influenced by the members of the family who form part of the current management or of the board of directors.
Lansberg, Perrow and Rogolsky (1988)	A business in which family members have legal control of the entity.
Ward (1989)	A business that will be passed on to the next generation of the family so that they can manage and control it.

Table 1- Definitions of Family Business – Source: Neubauer and Lank (1998)

From the definitions above, it can be noted that ownership, continuity and management seem to appear in almost every interpretation of the family business concept. So it can be concluded from all the definitions that succession is very important to the existence of family owned businesses.

In a family business, both family and business institutions overlap even though each has its goals, values and members. For example, the family's main purpose is to nurture and care for its members whereas a business has to do with producing and distributing goods or services. The goal of a family is mainly to develop as much as possible each

member regardless of each member's ability whereas the goal of a business is mainly to survive and get more profits. The different interests of family and business could create tension that leads to conflict. Relationships in a business with non related employees are less sensitive than relationships in a family. In a family business, relationships are more emotional so for example a performance review could become complicated. (Longenecker J. et al, 2006)

The figure below shows how people can be involved as family members, business employees, business owners, or any combinations of these.

Figure 1- Three Circle Model of Family Business - Source: Taguiri R and Davis J (1982)

Both the ownership and management circles are common to any type of business. However, the family circle is unique to family owned businesses in that it seeps into the ownership and management of the business. From the above diagram it can be seen that all three components interrelate and meet in the middle which signifies that at some point all three circles will be merged together. (Walsh G., 2011)

Walsh G (2011) suggests another variation to the Three Circle Model which denotes the influence that the family circle could have on the business.

Figure 2 - Altered Three Circle Model of Family Business - Source: Walsh G. (2011)

In this altered model the family circle is more prominent and has a greater effect on ownership and management. And so this model suggests that managing the family component is very important to the family.

2.2 Unique Characteristics of Family Businesses

Family owned businesses have unique characteristics that make them outperform non family counterparts. Many of the international and most successful companies keep a strong family identity such as H&M in Sweden, Clarks in UK, Samsung in Korea, to name a few (Gordon G & Nicholson N, 2008).

In Jordan, several families have made it big and continued their success throughout generations such as Shoman family (founders of Arab Bank), Al Manaseer Family (founders of Manaseer Group) and Nuqul family (founders of Nuqul Goup).

Davis and Green (2009) list the following unique characteristics that serve as advantages of family businesses:

- Optimism: Even in generally depressed business conditions, the owners of family businesses show a reasonably general sense of optimism. A survey done by the American Family Business Survey show that many family business owners are optimistic about their future and result figures prove that family owned businesses are indeed capable of weathering economic suffering and stabilizing the economy better than their non family owned counterparts. (Glavin B, Astrachan J & Green J, 2010)

- Loyalty: Family unity is very important to family businesses. After all, blood is thicker than water. Family members who work together have shared values. Research proves that the longest lived family owned business can draw on several methods originating from the bonding of family and business members (Pieper, 2007)

- Vigilance: No one is more attentive or watchful to the money like the owners themselves since most of the family's wealth is invested in the business which makes the connection both emotional and economical (Mallin C, 2007).

- Competitiveness: Family owned businesses try their best to increase their competitiveness. For example, family businesses investment's priority could be in the Information Technology infrastructure.

- Innovativeness: It has been found that family owned businesses put into practice more innovations than non family owned businesses. (Gudmundson D, Tower C, Hartman E, 2003) Even in businesses that are financially conservative, family owned businesses have displayed their ability to discard old products and services to create new ones. In such businesses it is the drive and energy of managing owners that motivates the innovation imperative and ability (Samson D, 2010).

- Nimbleness: Members of the family that have worked for many years together are more likely to move quickly and the family members are flexible in the several roles they are playing. Therefore, such businesses are more able to make faster and better decisions concerning the business (Rivers W, 2009).

An appealing unique characteristic of family owned SMEs is their light use of bureaucracy which gives them an aspect of speed and flexibility in solving their business problems. Elaborate decision-making methods become unnecessary due to their informality and intimacy. However, family owned SMEs do not recognize how the growth of the business is changing them. The irony here is that the self-same characteristic that gives family owned SMEs competitive advantage also contributes to the destructive conflict that could happen to the business. The lack of formal rules and systems facilitate easy and quick decision making but it can also be a problem to the introduction of good corporate governance. (Jordaan, 2012)

Keeping a connectedness to the past and all together becoming accustomed and living the founders' vision is a great and underexploited asset in family owned businesses. Also, the unity of family members affects stakeholders positively. For example, unified

members of a family are more possibly to share their own values with their employees. This overlap between the companies' values and the individuals could result in increased levels of commitment and loyalty. The American Family Business Survey reports that almost 85% of the respondents share values with their customers in the same way and such synchronization of values could improve the relationships and promote financial stability. (Mass Mutual Financial Group, 2010)

Even though these unique characteristics provide many advantages to the family owned business, there are still many disadvantages of a family owned business.

The following figure shows the disadvantages of family businesses model:

Figure 3 - Disadvantages of Family Businesses Model - Source: AMCML (2008)

A major characteristic of family businesses is that most of them fail to exist in the long run. Some of these attributes are similar to attributes that could make any other business fail such as scarce funds for growth, poor management, etc. However, the complexity of family businesses make it more difficult for them to in terms of corporate

governance than non-family owned businesses because of addition of the “family” variable. Also, all the family emotions and family matters add more complexity for the family businesses to deal with. Another characteristic of a family business that shows weakness is their informality. Usually there is very little interest in family businesses to run clear practices and procedures because most of them are run by the families themselves usually during the first and second generations, and very few survive to the third generation especially in the Middle East where less than 2% survive to the third generation (Makings G.S, 2009). This leads to inefficiencies as well as domestic conflicts which could threaten the continuity of the business. (IFC Corporate Governance, 2012)

2.3 Challenges to the Continuity of Family Business

Succession of a family business represents a challenge for many family businesses all over the world and non-more so than businesses in the Middle East. It is very difficult for such families to stay united and also remain successful as a business as well. (Makings G.S, 2009)

There are two main challenges related to succession in family owned businesses. The first challenge is that their heirs might not be as talented or interested as the founders might be which could affect the businesses growth compared to non family businesses (Burkat, Panunzi and Shleifer, 2003). What makes this problem worse, is that training in family businesses is not provided enough due to the lack of resources in terms of budgets and manpower; the basic reason is the obstacles of finding replacements to do

the work while the successor is in training and the relatively high costs of training. (MOP & UNDP, 2011)

The second challenge is the conflict among the family members that could paralyze the process of decision making and in some cases lead to underperformance. Bertrand and Schoar (2006) state that such conflict usually happen when more than one sibling is involved in the family business. The daily interactions among the family members within the business environment could lead to vicious power struggle. For example, managers of the family businesses in the Middle East in general usually feel disheartened when leading a family business and carrying the load from the rest of the family members. They usually see the situation that even though they are responsible for creating the wealth to family members, but there is no significant differentiation in their benefits from the rest of the family who make little contributions or no contribution at all to the business.

In addition to the above mentioned challenges, family owned businesses face succession challenges in the third generation juncture. Most critical challenge occurs in the transition phase from the second generation to the third. This occurs mainly because by then there are more family members included who hope to be part of the business. Sometimes, cousins are included where each has been raised according to different styles and points of views but more importantly due to differences in financial needs and their competencies. Furthermore, third generation family members could carry over unsolved problems from the second generation where their parents are too busy and over-involved in the conflict itself to try and solve the clash. (Davis P, 1997)

Most families in the MENA region were established in the 50's and so many of these businesses are now run by the second generation. The following figure shows the statistics of generation entrepreneurs.

Figure 4 - Family Businesses Generation Entrepreneurs - Source: AMCML (2011)

From the figure above it can be seen that family businesses in the MENA region are mostly run by the second generation. Based on the statistics above, it is most likely that these businesses fail as they are passed to the third generation because the companies will be then run by cousins with weaker family ties and obligations unlike being run by siblings with the same mother. (AMCML, 2011)

Also, in the Middle East and specifically in Jordan family businesses sometimes face other challenges because inheritance is distributed according to Shari'a law which fragments the shareholdings. In Jordan, off-shore trusts are not appropriate. However, the Shari'a law is only used when the owner is deceased and so Shari'a law does not

provide assistance to next generations on the succession of the business and family unity. (Makings G.S, 2009)

There is a gap in literature in this area of research where this study will try to fill in. However, one study by Booz and Company (2009) that focuses on succession in GCC lists five crises that challenge the standing of GCC family businesses: Control crises, succession crises, dilution crises, competitive crises and economic crises. The first three crises are persistent challenges that are specific to GCC family owned businesses.

The control crisis refers to the wide diversification that holds back the ability for family businesses to control their future competitiveness. This is not much relevant to Jordanian family businesses because the Jordanian market is relatively small and very few businesses have successfully diversified into several sectors.

The succession crisis implies that the transition of family businesses into the third generation will put pressure on the cohesiveness of the family. Booz and Company (2009) illustrate the succession challenges to GCC families as follows:

Figure 5 - Succession Challenges – Source: Booz & Company (2009)

In the figure above, the three intricacies specific to the GCC families are very relevant to Jordanian families. Jordanian families are usually large in number and family businesses are tied by the traditions and Sharia law.

2.4 Succession Planning: What Family Owned Businesses Need to Survive and Thrive

To understand succession in family owned businesses, one needs to understand what succession actually is. The succession of family business has been defined as the handing over of management control to family members (Gasson R and Errington, 1993). Beckhard and Burke (1983, p.3) define succession in a family business as the “the passing of the leadership baton from the founder-owner to a successor who will either be a family member or a non-family member; that is, a 'professional manager”.

However, Barry (1975) divided this leadership “baton” into 2 axes: ownership and management which implies that there is a range of combinations of both management and ownership among the family available to the business in transition. Liebowitz B (2013) state that “at least four factors define succession planning: the needs of the owner and spouse, the requirements of the business and its management team, the demands of ownership transition, and concerns about inheritance”.

Succession is not an event but an ongoing process that takes years of planning. A good succession process provides family businesses the opportunity to choose an effective leader who is able to revive the business (Ibrahim A. et al, 1999).

2.4.1 The Succession Process

In literature, the succession process is explained by 3 particular steps (Stavrou, 1999; Poutziouris and Chittenden, 1996; Handler, 1989):

1. The preparation of offspring for the leadership role early in life and before joining the business;
2. The integration of offspring into the business in several roles;
3. And finally assuming the leadership role in the business.

Longenecker J. et al (2006) state the following stages in the succession process of a family business:

- I. Pre-business Stage: A prospective heir becomes familiar with the business early on while growing up. The young potential successor accompanies his/ her parent

to the business. This stage does not include any formal planning. It only forms the basis for the more planned stages of the process later on.

- II. **Introductory Stage:** This stage also occurs before the successor is old enough to work in the business. However, it differs in that this stage parents introduce the child to certain individuals within the business that are associated directly or indirectly to the business itself, or to any other aspect of the business.
- III. **Introductory Functional Stage:** This is when the successor starts working as a part-time employee usually in vacations. It involves tasks from different functional areas as time goes by.
- IV. **Functional Stage:** This is the actual entry of the successor into the business. This is when he/ she start working full-time at the business, usually following the conclusion of his/ her formal education.
- V. **Advanced Functional Stage:** This stage is when the successor assumes managerial responsibilities. In this stage the successor only directs the work of others but does not manage the business.
- VI. **Early Succession Stage:** In this stage the successor is named the general manager of the business or the president. He/ she exercise overall direction but a parent is still in the background. Here, the predecessor might still be reluctant to renounce the decision making and the successor has not completely mastered the complications of the position.
- VII. **Mature Succession Stage:** In this stage the transition is complete. The successor becomes the leader both in title and function. Sometimes this occurs when the predecessor dies.

Lansberg (1988) suggests that for a succession process to be successful, mentors need to know the difference between mentoring and parenting. It is important to find just the right balance between mentoring and parenting.

Handler (1989) refers to the case of the absence of succession planning as one of the main reasons behind the downfall of family owned businesses. Having a successful succession plan gives family businesses a competitive edge over their non-family counterparts by allowing the continual use of accumulated characteristics understanding of the family members. (Bjuggren and Sund, 2001) Ram and Jones (2002) state that the combination of the family member's loyalty and trust along with the inside knowledge held by family members provides them with certain competencies that are needed to run an effective business, and also help the family members create the resources and capabilities needed to generate a competitive advantage.

Also, a good succession plan improves the value of business by making sure that it keeps the most talented successors. Usually, the most talented flee the family businesses seeking better opportunities. Some of the family businesses encourage this so that the other family members who can't take care of themselves will have something to do. This could damage the business and its integrity. (Aranoff C, Mclure S and Ward J, 2003)

According to Lansberg (1988), the planning of succession, or even the lack of it, is the only most significant reason why 1st generation family-owned businesses usually don't go on and survive to the next. That is a lot of work is needed in this field.

Morris et al (1996) propose main areas that must be addressed in succession planning which are: the preparation of heirs, the relationship between the family and business members, planning actions. They discovered that in successful family owned businesses, the heirs were prepared in terms of experience and education. They also revealed that successful businesses have positive relationships among each other. Moreover, they state that successful businesses have informal control activities with minimum dependence on outside advisors.

2.4.2 Selection of Successors

In a family business, different considerations apply when choosing a successor than non family businesses. In a family owned business, decisions concerning succession are complicated by emotional factors that are not present in non family businesses. In some cases, it is very easy to select a successor when there is only one candidate that has shined and demonstrated the necessary skills to lead the business. But oftentimes the situation is more difficult than this.

So how does a family business choose its successor? Wasserman E (2010) states that “a good succession plan needs to include criteria for the successor that reflects the needs of the business in the future”.

If there are several candidates that were recognized as potential leaders, then a group of trusted advisors can be asked for recommendations. The committee can observe the candidates over a period of time and watch their work. Family owned businesses, however, need to consult with specialists in business succession such as attorneys,

accountants and tax planners in order to fully understand the implications about selecting successors. (Wasserman E., 2010)

Aronoff, McClure, and Ward (2003) state that there are a number of plans that needs to be developed to guarantee a successful transition such as a business plan, mission statement, owners estate plan and a succession plan. In the selection process, it is important to communicate the succession decision.

In the preparation process of successors, predecessors need to set aside natural tendencies (Aronoff and Ward, 1991). Cabrera-Suarez K, De Saa-Perez, P and Garcia-Almeida D (2001) emphasize the importance of having good working relationships between the predecessor and successor in the transfer of power. The incumbent should be prepared of letting go of the management of the business. Also, the incumbent must hand over the responsibilities and allow the successor to make decisions.

Chrisman, Chua and Sharma (1998) studied the desired characteristics of successors and developed six categories which are relationship to the incumbent; relationships to other family members; family standing; competence; personality traits; and current involvement in the family business. They concluded that the most important qualities in a successor are integrity and commitment.

In addition, it is common that some predecessors favor their first-borns especially male over other qualified family members. However, in a survey performed by Chriman, Chua and Sharma (1998) they found that both gender and the birth order were not so important.

Basically, family owned businesses need to have a plan in advance to make sure the family business is sustained to the following generations. The following important factors need to be considered to ensure a successful succession among the family: family ownership, hiring professional managers/ family directors, successor's education level, founder/successor's age and gender. (Amran N. & Ahmad A., 2010)

2.4.3 Successor Education

The education background of the family business manager is very important to ensure the continuity of the family business and enhance its performance. In previous generations, family owners used to have less educational degrees (Brockuas & Nord, 1979). These days, the educational trend is changing. Potential successors are being sent abroad to pursue their education. The potential successors themselves are opting for college and working for other companies before joining the family business. (Amran N. & Ahmad A., 2010) Informal training given to the potential successors within the family could substitute formal training courses given by professional institutions (Lentz B & Laband D, 1990). However in this competitive and globalized market, more focus must be given to training successors. (Ibrahim A and Ellis W, 1994)

The importance of successors' education has sprung for the recent realization of the families' responsibilities in advancing their intellectual capital. Therefore, for most family businesses, education and knowledge sharing is paramount (Hughes J., 2004).

For example, some families persist that their children work outside the company for several years in order to bring back to the family business their gained knowledge to benefit the family business from their experience.

2.5 Resistance to Succession Planning

Despite the importance of succession, statistics show that succession in family businesses is still a problematic issue. Studies have shown that only 30% of family owned businesses survive the transition from the first generation to the second and only 10% carry on to the third generation (Beckhard and Dyer, 1983). Even though succession planning is very important, it is not often executed by family owned businesses although theorists such as Christensen, Dyer and Handler have all agreed that the continuity of a family business from one generation to the next generation depends greatly on the succession planning (Handler W, 1994).

A study revealed that only 28 percent of family businesses that were surveyed actually had a succession plan. (Lifeline of Success, 1999) Another study by Kertesz and Atalaya (1999) found that almost 70 percent of family businesses resisted the preparation for succession.

Founders of family businesses usually resist succession planning due to their inability to dissociate from the business because of the following reasons: their identity is wrapped up with the business (Kets de Vries, 1998), their lack of interest, their lack of ability to seek consultation. Also, the lack of trust and communication might perplex the process of succession.

Other researchers have attributed the founders' resistance to succession planning to some other factors such as their strong sense of attachment to their business and their fear of retirement. (Ibrahim A, Soufani K and Lam J, 2001)

The figure below shows a model of resistance to succession in a family business (Handler W, 1994):

Figure 6 - A Model of Resistance to Succession in a Family Business - Source: Handler W (1994)

It is critical in succession to take careful note of the timing. The succession planning would be useless if there were no heirs or the heirs were not interested in the business. Handler and Kram (1988, p.376) state that “if an owner's decision to retire cannot be juxtaposed with an heir's appropriateness and readiness to take over, then succession may not occur under the best possible conditions”.

There are other factors that could complicate the succession process other than the founders' resistance to succession planning such as conflict among family members, lack of a clear selection of a successor and power imbalances. Also, there are factors at the organizational level that affect the succession process such as the structure of business and the organizational culture. (Handler W, 1994)

2.6 Corporate Governance

According to Mahmood S. (2008) there is no exact definition for corporate governance. It is basically the system by which businesses are controlled.

Corporate governance limits the conflicts that could happen internally and ensure a smooth transition of ownership to heirs. Abou-el-fatouh (2009) states that "Corporate governance framework ensures that shareholders are freed from executive and administrative duties. As a result, conflicts among business owners who assume management roles in the organization would be reduced to a greater extent particularly in organizations owned by few number of shareholders where the distinction between ownership and management capacity is blurred".

Family businesses in the Middle East are complacent about corporate governance; even though, strong governance is an essential element to any business. In a survey conducted by EIU-Barclays in 2008, it stated that less than 1 in 5 family businesses considered governance as an essential characteristic for the success of their business. (AMCML, 2011)

In general, the adoption of a corporate awareness framework is not common in Jordan or even in the Middle East for that matter. This is because of the misconception that adopting corporate governance requires high costs with no guarantees that these costs will generate benefits to the family business. (Abou-el-fatouh H, 2009)

The additional costs of applying corporate governance come from appointing independent directors, developing internal control system and performing external audits. On the other hand, these costs are outweighed by the long term benefits acquired from applying corporate governance. For example, investors would have more confidence in investing in companies that have a good governance foundation ready in place. Such investments could help family-owned businesses to internationalize and venture new markets. This will help develop businesses to promote innovation and deepen technology. Good corporate governance help the business achieve its corporate goals through a more efficient use of resources. (Mahmood S, 2008)

Mahmood S (2008) proposes the following framework for corporate governance:

1. Initiate a debate among the key stakeholders concerning the importance of corporate governance and its need for the business in order to increase awareness on the subject matter. The implications of corporate governance are also discussed in this phase to the business.
2. Develop the code of corporate governance. The main elements of a code usually include a board of directors, corporate financial reporting, independent external audits and internal audits.

3. Begin the process of capacity building. Here, training workshops must be conducted to all stakeholders even the owners themselves.

The table below shows the drivers and resistors to corporate governance in any business:

Drivers for corporate governance	Resisters to corporate governance
• Focus on the interests of the organisation	• Self-interest, hidden agendas
• Need to allocate power to get results	• Urge to consolidate power
• Need to achieve sustainability	• Desire to have quick results
• Managing risks	• Manipulating risks
• Picking 'horses for courses' to win	• Protecting favourites
• Deregulation/giving freedom to act	• Regulation/control
• Ensuring security of agreements	• Ends justify the means/utilitarianism
• Maintaining high standards	• Relativism – 'what suits'/complacency
• Ensuring fairness between stakeholders	• Courting popularity for own ends
• Openness	• Secrecy
• Innovation/self-renewal of the organization	• Resistance to change
• Commitment	• Disengagement – 'too much trouble'
• Leadership from all stakeholders	• Napoleonic leadership
• Trust/reputation	• Distrust/protectiveness

Figure 7 - Forces impacting corporate governance - Source: Davies A. (2011)

2.7 Theoretical Models on Succession and Family Performance

A theoretical framework is the “system of concepts, assumptions, expectations, beliefs and theories that supports and informs a research” (Maxwell, 2005, p.30) It is in fact the underlying structure or more likely the scaffold of a study.

[Table 2](#) shows the few researchers that used theoretical framework to construct their studies and their key findings. These researchers have used samples from the US, Canada, UK and Australia. None of the papers used samples from the Middle East in

their studies. However, the key findings can be useful to any family business regardless of their location around the world.

Author	Objective	Theoretical Base	Key findings
Zajac (1990)	Offer a conceptual model of the relationship between CEO and performance.	Organizational and agency theories	Firms with insider CEOs tend to be significantly more profitable than firms with outsider CEOs.
Daily and Dollinger (1992)	Compare FOBs vs. NFOBs, the advantages of ownership and control alignment.	Agency theory	Weak evidence that family run firms present performance advantages over the professionally run firms.
Goldberg (1996)	Examine why some family successors grow revenues and profit more than others.	n/a	Successor effectiveness is associated to incumbent's mentoring, good relationship, and early introduction in the businesses.
Morris <i>et al.</i> (1997)	How successful transitions influence firm performance.	Life-cycle and system theories	FOB smooth transitions when successors are better prepared, good relationships, and succession planning, but not result in better performance.
Smith and Amoako-Adu (1999)*	Examine the relationship between pre- and post-performance, and succession in FOBs.	n/a	There is some evidence that poor corporate performance leads to the appointment of non-family members. Long-term performance is superior with non-family successors.
Lauterbach <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Identify the factors influence successions, and measure post-performance.	Agency theory	External successions are more likely in small firms, in firms with poor economic performance. External successors, superior post-performance.
McCounaughy (2000)	To test if family CEOs have superior incentives for maximizing firm value.	Agency theory	Founding-family CEOs are paid less and are less sensitive to performance. FOBs have to pay non-family CEOs more to get what a family CEO do.
Morck <i>et al.</i> (2000)	Investigate whether control by small number of wealthy families may be suboptimal.	Agency theory	Control by heirs results in lower returns on sales and assets, and with growth that is less than or equal to that observed in other comparable firms.
Pérez-González (2001)	Evaluate consequences in firm performance of naming a family member CEO.	Agency theory	Family heirs hurt the firm performance and consistently underperform.
Pérez-Gonzales (2002)	Examine the impact of inherited control on firm's performance.	n/a	Firms with inherited control undergo large declines in return on assets and market-to-book value ratios, not experienced by unrelated CEOs.
Shen and Cannella (2003)	Examines investor reaction to relay successions.	Agency theory	Appointment of an heir has a positive wealth effect. Nonrelay inside succession negatively affect shareholder wealth; positive wealth effect for outside succession.
King (2003)	Evaluate performance after succession is attributable to differences with predecessors.	Systems Theory Potential capability	Successor's potential capability is important for firm performance. Commitment and skills brought to the business are also important.
Wang <i>et al.</i> (2004)	The relationship between succession and performance in FOBs.	n/a	Successor's development and inter-generational affect profitability in small firms; in medium firms are succession planning and development.
Huson <i>et al.</i> (2004)	Examine CEO turnover and firm performance.	n/a	Accounting measures of performance relative to other firms deteriorate prior to CEO turnover and improve thereafter.
Behn <i>et al.</i> (2005)	Examine whether the equity markets value firms that have a succession plan in place.	n/a	Firms with an heir designated on the date of death of the CEO have significantly higher cumulative abnormal returns on the date of death than firms that have not identified an heir apparent.
Kotey (2005)	Examine differences between family and non-family SMEs and performance.	n/a	Small family firms achieved greater profits than their non-family counterparts, although this disparity disappeared at the medium level.
Rowe <i>et al.</i> (2005)	Examine the impact of leader succession on organizational performance.	Organizational learning and resource-based view.	Leader succession does affect performance and that leaders do matter. Timing seems to be important in succession and that leaders need time develop organization specific skills.

* The only investigation on pre-performance and succession in FOBs

Table 2 - Succession and Firm Performance. Source: Bocatto E (2006)

2.7.1 Agency Theory

The agency theory is the main theoretical basis used to explain and better understand the relationship between manager and owners of the business. The basic idea behind this theory is that managers who are non-owners of a business will not look after affairs of the business as the owners themselves.

One critical finding by Smith and Amoako-Adu (1999) is that the long term return on assets gets better when nominating non family members over family members. The agency theory is in favor of using professionalization and it considers the formal governance and control systems as a method to aligning the manager/ owner's actions and interests.

A non family member will not have the same motivation and incentive as an owner of the business will have and might engage in self serving actions. In order to avoid possible conflict of interests, family business owners can install non family managers and give them controls and policies to limit the effect of conflict of interest and so create agency costs. Many specialists in this field think that family owned businesses have less agency costs due to the shared ownership functions. (Alderson K., 2011)

Founded on the agency theory, ownership by family members minimizes the agency problems because "shares are in the hands of agents who have special relations with other decision agents that allow agency problems to be controlled without separation of the management and control decisions" (Amran N. & Ahmad A., 2010). Moreover, according to Fama and Jensen (1983) family members have the advantage of supervising and disciplining the agents because they have the several scopes of exchange with one another over a long prospect.

Shleifer and Vishny (1997) state that the risk of free-riding is more likely to disappear because the ownership is concentrated in the hands of family members. According to Jensen & Meckling (1976) and Fama & Jensen (1983) the involvement of family in business ownership might avoid the dilemma of the agent's potential exploitative behavior towards the principal, and reduce the costs of supervision. Whereas, Gorriz and Fumus show that the agency costs are reduced when the shares are focused on a few a small number of owners that do all the decisions.

2.7.2 System theory and family business:

The system theory is usually the theory used to scholarly study family businesses. But it remains pervasive till today. The systems theory models a family business as an overlap, intersection and independent three subsystems of management, family and ownership. (Davis P, 1983) The emphasis of using this theory is focused on mechanisms of integration used to decide results of the bigger system that gives mutual benefits to all system members. (Poza E, 2010)

As the family business grows and in its transitional phase to next generations, it is important for all the three systems to stay balanced. (Roang S., 2010) Daily C and Dollinger M (1992) state the importance of properly aligning the ownership and control of the family business, because historically it has lead to better outcomes.

The intersection of the three circles clarifies the potential competitive advantage of family businesses and their shortcomings. Family members who are in different circles can have differences when they are looked at with the 3 subsystems in mind. For

example, if a family member is in two circles (an owner but not an employee), then he/she might be leaning towards a considered buyout offer than a family member who is in three circles (an owner and management member). Another example, is an entrepreneurial owner with full control and ownership who is in three circles might not be keen to paying high salaries to employees within two circles who are family members but not owners. (Alderson K., 2011)

2.8 Succession in Jordanian Family Businesses

It is believed in Jordan and in the Middle East in general that family business is a way to enhance the family name and social standing of the family rather than just generating money. (Fahed-Sreih, 2006)

Even though Jordan is currently experiencing greater freedom, changing of roles and empowerment of women, selection of heirs to the business is still based on passing the business to the eldest born son in the family because male born sons are the ones that will carry on the name of the family. And so women of the family can work in the family business but they do not run and manage the business. However, women can manage the business if there are no male sons in the family.

2.9 Jordan's Cultural and Religious Impact on Family Businesses

Jordan, officially the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, is a small country in the Middle East with very limited resources. Its official language is Arabic. However, English is widely spoken throughout the country. Islam is the official religion of the population. Due

to the unsettling political situation of the Middle East region, Jordan is home to many refugees from Palestine, Iraq and Syria.

In Jordan, families are generally conservative and family ties in Jordan are so strong that business owners are obliged to hire family members even if those who are not fit.

Being polite is extremely important in Jordan especially having respect for the elders because age plays significant part in culture. So it is the custom to take advice of the elders when making decisions. This becomes complicated in family businesses in which the multiple roles make the situations complex. On the other hand, the strong bonds among family members are reflected on the business which encourages inherent trust for one another.

Islamic values and laws are a crucial part of the society in Jordan. The Islamic beliefs imply that Jordanians are inclined to be family oriented, rule abiding and hospitable. These social duties affect the business dealings in the Jordanian business world.

Jordan follows the Sharia law when it comes to inheritance. However, Sharia law applies only in the case of death of the antecessor. But it is acceptable in Islam to have a will (Al Wasiya). An Islamic will is executed before distributing the estate among heirs according to Sharia. But it is advised that before writing a will, one must consult with a legal expert or Islamic scholar to insure the will complies with Islamic laws and laws of the country of residence. (Hussain A, 2013)

Family is the most important component in the Jordanian culture. Supporting family members to one another is always a source of pride and honor.

Saving face is integral in Jordanian culture and thus conflict is usually addressed privately to avoid any public embarrassment.

In Jordan and the Middle East in general, philanthropic values are very strong and deeply rooted. Many of the family businesses in the region support initiatives that involve the underprivileged and want to give back to the society. (Barclays Wealth, 2009)

Chapter 3 METHODOLOGY

To gain a better understanding of succession in family businesses in Jordan, this research examines the processes that have led to the succession of 8 companies to the next generation. The research follows a case study approach to identify the problems, causes, and consequences of succession in family businesses that would help in coming to conclusions on the remedies of the succession problem in Jordan.

First, the data was collected through conducting a study of any public documents and then doing face-to-face interviews or telephone interviews.

This chapter includes the research gap, questions, framework, approach, design and methods (including sampling, piloting, validity and reliability).

3.1 Research Gap

After assessing the research literature on succession, there are still some gaps to what represents effective succession. Succession in both family owned businesses and non family businesses has been widely discussed in literature. However, few have studies have discussed the succession in family businesses within the Arab context. Arabs have cultural and religious obligations that could affect the succession process. There is limited research on the cultural traditions in the Arab world that affect succession of family owned businesses.

Many researchers have tackled the subject of succession in family business as a problem that needs to be solved. However, there is very little literature on how to

incorporate succession into the daily routine of businesses and treat it as an ongoing process.

3.2 Research Questions

The researcher intends to answer the following questions:

Theme 1: Family Control and Leadership for Succession

- In what ways can owners try to balance the strive to keep family's control over the company the objective of the company's growth?
- Does solid governance help resolve conflict issues among family members?
- Will clear policies for selecting the fit family member ensure leadership transition without disrupting the growth of the business?
- Is the lack of longevity attributed to the poor succession management process that hinders the transfer of the business from one generation to the next?
- What means are there to promote successful leadership succession amongst family businesses?

Theme 2: Resistance to Change

- How can family owned businesses adapt to change?
- Does the level of understanding on how corporate governance can affect the way people react to change?
- How can family businesses deal with resistance to change from employees and successors?

Theme 3: Culture and Succession

- What is the impact of cultural factors on successful succession in a family business?

3.3 Research Framework

In this study, the researcher used the Systems and Agency Theories to analyze the case studies and discuss findings. The systems theory is important to understand the overlap between the family system and business system.

The chosen theoretical frameworks help advance the research on family businesses in the use of governance and strategic planning. By analyzing the above-mentioned theories the researcher will be able to draw an inclusive picture on the involvement of managers/ owners and the mechanisms the theories identify.

Also, the researcher will use a succession framework demonstrated in the diagram below:

Figure 8 - Model of Succession in Family Business - Source: Longenecker J. and Schoen J. (1978) "Management Succession in the Family Business" Journal of Small Business Management Vol. 16 pp. 1-6

3.4 Research Approach

The researcher performed a qualitative research in this study to gain a rich understanding of family businesses founders' or successors' experiences, emotions and behaviors.

In this study the researcher uses both inductive and deductive research approaches to gain in depth understanding and to allow some flexibility to the structure of research throughout the course of research.

In an inductive research approach, a hypothesis is not made pre-determinately. The data collected through interviews, focus groups or observation. However, the data is not converted into numbers and is not analyzed statistically. Whereas, by using a deductive research approach, I will be conforming existing theories.

Morrow and Smith (2000) state that the purpose of qualitative research is to understand and describe participant meaning. Creswell (1998) defines qualitative research as an investigation process of comprehension based on “different methodological traditions of inquiry that explore a social or human problem. The research builds a complex, holistic pictures, analyzes words, reports detailed views of informants, and conducted the study in natural setting.” (Creswell, 1998, p15)

The hypothesis is generated during the collection of data, and the analysis is more likely to be subjective. According to McConney A, Rudd A, and Ayers R. (2002) and Hines (2000) in a qualitative research, the researcher becomes the means of data collection and so results could differ significantly dependent on the person conducting the study.

Using a qualitative method helps the researcher of this study generate rich and detailed data that leaves the participants' viewpoints intact.

Despite the downside of the qualitative method of being time consuming and laborious to collect and analyze the data (Hines, 2000), qualitative data is the most appropriate for

this research since it gathers rich data in the way of attitudes, feelings, and motivations of the subjects (McDaniel and Gates, 2007).

3.5 Research Design

The researcher in this study utilizes a case study design so to empirically investigate 8 local family owned businesses in Jordan so to study their views and practices on succession.

3.6 Research Methods

The aim of the researcher of this research is to help family owned businesses realize that succession is not just a problem that needs solving in Jordan but it is also an ongoing process that needs to be incorporated into the businesses' daily lives.

In order to do so, the researcher made thorough interviews and observations to the studied group of participants in a way that explores their practices from within and attends to their daily routines. These methods are designed to better understand the meanings assigned by the people on social occurrences and to clarify behaviors.

(Taruwanga P, 2011)

The researcher focuses on eight family-owned businesses that have been running for at least 2 generations. The researcher conducted exclusive interviews to the owners of the businesses that are in management of firms in addition to observations on how they work.

The interviews are conducted in Arabic (the local language of the participants) and the researcher asked clear and simple questions for everyone to understand with open-ended questions. The interviews are held by the researcher in a way that engages conversation and goes off at tangents to give insight into the interviewees' points of views.

Background and context review of documents is used to perform content analysis. Accordingly, the artifact of the family business owners group was interpreted. The used method by the researcher is nonreactive and thus did not disturb any of the participants in the study.

There are some limitations to interviewing participants in research. Some of the participants may not be cooperative and might not feel comfortable sharing important and sensitive details. However in this research, the questions asked invoked long narratives and questions are framed well.

All participants were well informed by the researcher on the nature of the research and were provided with complete information concerning the study.

3.7 Procedure

This section describes how data is collected by the researcher in this study and then analyzed in order to come up with useful findings on the subject.

3.7.1 Data Collection

The researcher collected data through in-depth interviews to founders/ managers of and their successors of Jordanian family owned businesses. The sample comprised of 8 Jordanian companies selected by the researcher.

The procedure was as follows:

1. The researcher selected and identified eight local family owned companies for the in-depth interviews.
2. The researcher sent emails and placed calls to set up the interview appointments to start in February 2013.
3. The researcher sent ahead the interview schedule through email to all the participants. The interview schedule can be found in Appendix 1.
4. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews that lasted around 40 minutes each. All interviews were held face to face in each participant's headquarters in Amman, Jordan. Interviews were recorded and stored for future record.
5. The researcher thanked each and every participant for their much valued time.

In the early stages of the interviews, the researcher established a positive atmosphere for communicating and discussing the interview questions. The researcher digitally recorded all interviews for reference later in the analysis of the data collected process. The order of questions was set by the researcher in a way that made the interviewee communicate comfortably.

All participants were well aware of the confidentiality of the data collected for their privacy protection. All names were agreed to be held confidential as well as the

company names. Accordingly, the participants were more than willing to answer the interview questions once they guaranteed their privacy.

However, one of the participants is a close relative to the researcher which threatened to cause conflict. However, the researcher acted in a non-judgmental manner and assured participant family members of their privacy.

3.7.2 Data Analysis

The analysis of the data collected from the interviews of 8 Jordanian family owned businesses was done by the researcher first by analyzing the responses of the interviewed company managers within the frameworks constructed in the literature review, and second by illuminating the differences and similarities of data collected from the interviews and so recommendations were given on succession planning.

3.7.3 Reliability and Validity

Validity is a strong point of qualitative research whereas “reliability and generalizability play a minor role in qualitative inquiry” (Creswell, J. W, 2003, p.195). According to White (2000) validity ponders on whether the research design addresses the research questions and objectives of the research in full.

In this research the researcher ensured validity through two strategies which are triangulation and member checking.

Triangulation is a concept concerned with testing evidence through different sources of data and uses this evidence to justify the research themes. (Creswell ,2003) Data triangulation entails the collection of data from various sources over a different time span. However since this research is restricted to 9 months of time only, it would not be possible to use different time scales. Instead, the researcher used a different type of data triangulation by interviewing family members of different stages in their business career; the predecessors and successors to ensure equal split of interviews between successors and predecessors.

The use of member-checking ensures that the resulted information makes sense to the participants of research and that they also agree to it.

All interviews were conducted in the Arabic language (mother tongue language in Jordan) with the use of basic and simple vocabulary that is familiar to all participants.

Chapter 4 RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Chapter 4 gives detailed case studies on Jordanian family businesses' succession history and succession process. Each case study is compared against the succession models discussed in the literature review.

Also in this chapter, important and interesting findings are discussed that lead to the guidelines provided in the chapter.

4.1 Case Study Analysis

In this sub-chapter 8 different case studies are discussed. For confidentiality reasons, each company is given an alias name as well as the family members.

Case Study 1: Fashion Trends

Fashion Trends Company was first established in 2005 by Mr. Salah. The company sells casual clothing in one of Jordan's most popular markets. The objective of the company was to be a family business that imports good quality garments that are accessible to all. Mr. Salah ensures the best competitive prices by building excellent relations with suppliers and buying in bulk which allows him to get the lowest prices possible.

The Salah family is made up of 7 members: Mr. Salah, his wife, an older son, three daughters and a younger son. Mr. Salah has always focused on Zaid the older son to

be the successor of the business being the first born of the family. Zaid was involved in the business early on in his life. Back in school, Mr. Salah would ask Zaid to go to the store and observe the work done. Zaid was not given any tasks; he simply observed how inventory was done, how salesmen handled customers and how the cash register works.

In 2008, Fashion Trends opened up two other branches in different local Jordanian markets but with different names (not under the brand name of the company) that targeted middle income women. This decision for expansion was not due to market studies but because the new store locations were given at a very good price that Mr. Salah could not resist the offer.

Also in 2008, Zaid graduated from college and was very eager and fully engaged in the business in a managerial position as a Store Manager. Older employees were offended by taking tasks from Zaid. Employees considered him to be younger and less experienced to give “orders” and that he was in this position just because he is the owners’ son but Zaid was very passionate about the family business. Zaid resolved this conflict by being friends with the employees, understanding their problems but at the same time enforcing stricter rules at the company than his own father. Eventually employees took him seriously.

Zaid struggles to this day from the lack of governance. The company has no specific structure. The company does not have clear standards, goals, HR policies, roles and responsibilities for each person holding a job. Zaid knows for a fact that if he changes anything in this regard, there will be resistance to change from the employees that

would affect work. Mr. Salah is not enthusiastic to any change because this is how the business was going for the past 8 years and he does not believe change would help but would make things even worse.

The company is in its transitional phase to moving completely to the second generation. However, all final decisions are made by Mr Salah as he is the founder and the older person in this equation. Succession is based on the tradition that the eldest son takes over after the father is out of the picture.

Due to the bad economic situations in Jordan for the past years, Fashion Trends had to close 2 branches and focus on only one branch and now they are struggling to keep the original store from closing.

Zaid's future plan is to change the line of business and go into the wholesale business instead of the retail by keeping the family business name and take advantage of all the connections they have built over the years.

Case Study 2: Elia Group

Elia group was established in 1952 by Mr. John Elia as a modest business that imports and distributes foodstuff. It is a privately owned family business that employs around 6000 employees. It is a well recognized diversified industrial conglomerate that is comprised of 29 companies both regionally and globally with export activities to more than 45 global markets.

Mr. John Elia wanted to keep the business in the family and so in the early years of the business, he implanted the idea of managing the business to his eldest son Edward. Every time Edward would visit the company, his father would point to the big desk at the back of his office and state that this would be “all yours” one day. The idea of running the business was implanted in Edwards head at a young age and he was fascinated by the idea.

After getting his industrial engineering university degree from the USA, Edward was encouraged by his father to continue his studies and get an MBA degree. In 1985, Edward officially joined the business and was fully engaged in the business. With his industrial engineering education background, Edward started implementing the things he learned in school into the business. Edward would be the first to arrive at the factory and the last one to leave. His father gave him the support to do all the changes needed.

Edward worked on every machine in the factory. He noticed that employees had no reference to get to when having questions or when new employees arrived to the plants and thus time was wasted on answering questions and teaching employees simple procedures. Thus, Edward documented all processes, procedures and safety protocols. He also created user manuals for each and every machine in the factory.

Employees were frustrated with all the changes made. Old employees were not happy with the fact that a young person would come and tell them what to do and ask them to things differently. Edward decided that to move forward, they needed new blood. He hired new, young and educated employees. Family members were very happy with Edward's work and they would seek his advice constantly. Edward felt pressured by the

family that they have put too much faith in him because they thought he had the solution to every problem encountered.

Edward attended a conference on corporate governance and was very intrigued by the concept. He discovered that over 70% of the things said in the conference we already applied in the business but without actually knowing it was called corporate governance. What was evolved in Elia group was done in response to the actual needs and challenges on the ground.

The company grew into multiple conglomerates that John and Edward could not possibly run on their own. The family's hands-on role in more than 20 companies was creating a bottleneck problem which was then solved by putting the family in place, empowering non family members into executive positions and creating a family protocol. The family protocol was created to avoid and ease tensions that could arise between the family members. For example, one of the protocols states that a family member could manage one of the companies for a maximum of three years period. This protocol was set for credibility reasons; having a set period for management would lessen the blame and pointing fingers if anything goes wrong in a business. The family protocol also has a clear selection process for family members and successors to ensure qualified members enter the business.

They formed a board that was comprised of key family members, and external consultants where John was appointed Chairman and Edward was appointed vice chairman of the board.

In 2004, Elia family separated management from ownership. However, this has not taken away the family aspect of the business. Edward, to this day, still takes care of any challenges and major daily decisions of the business. Decisions are made through the board but the final and utmost decision is up to the board chairman. Nowadays, John elia the board chairman is sick and thus Edward is the acting chairman of the board. After meeting and consulting with the board, he makes his decisions accordingly. However, the daily decisions are made by the non family CEO of the group. Only major decisions are done by the board.

Edward's future envision of the business is to completely separate the family's role from the daily routines of the business and keep the family's involvement to annual board and family meetings. His only concern is to try and keep the original founders visions and culture in the business without having coming generations lose track and astray from the founders visions.

Case Study 3: T&G Group

T&G group emerged in 1993 as a result of several successful investments and ventures in a number of sectors. The company was founded by two brothers from the Omar family.

In 2003, the company won the franchising of famous cinnamon rolls and coffee places due to their commitment to high standards and quality. The founders were managing the franchise until 2007 when one of the founders' son, Kamal was appointed manager to the franchise. Kamal had just graduated from university with a business degree but

lacked the experience. He had to learn from the employees how work was done. Even though observing work from employees was beneficial, Kamal was not satisfied. He believed there were other ways to do the job more efficiently. Kamal decided, to get training abroad in the original franchise country. He learned to work every coffee machine, every baking technique, he worked at point of sale, warehouse and even delivery; in other words, he learned every aspect of the business.

Kamal went back to Jordan to apply the things he learned. One of the main challenges Kamal faced in getting into the business was dealing with uneducated people. Many of the workers in the food and beverage sector were uneducated people that at the end of the day want to make ends meet. So seeking advice from experts around Kamal was not so beneficial. Also, a major challenge faced Kamal was the un-systemized back office. Picking up the pieces after the founders was a little difficult for Kamal and so sought consult from experts. In 2010, Kamal hired an expert in the field for 6 months so organize the business. The expert put standards, HR policies, a mission and a vision for the business and an organization structure. Having systemized the management of the business made suppliers more comfortable dealing with the business and customers took the business more seriously. Family members encouraged Kamal to stay in the family business and had very high hopes for him. Employees were not very pleased with all the changes done especially to come from someone young as Kamal.

Currently, Kamal is the acting General Manager of the company. He's been in this role for almost 2 years. As the GM he makes the final decision along with his older cousin who is the chairman of the family board. They work through board meetings. To reach to a final decision say for example opening a new store location, a board meeting is

held where the founders, board chairman, general manager and financial council meet to brainstorm and discuss the profitability, successfulness and budgeting, construction equipment and staffing of implementing the new idea.

Kamal's future envisions are to open up to 6 new store locations around the country, and by 2015 to expand into an additional 10 locations. However, his hands-on management of the stores is very tiring. He also plans to create divisions and divide the work load to managers where he will follow up with each manager only. He also plans to localize some of the ingredients they usually use for their products.

Kamal plans to build an excellent company structure so that in the long future they can sell it out to an investor. He also tends to keep the succession process as it is; where junior family members start training in the company early on and then work their way up and so successors are decided according to their competence.

Case Study 4: S2M Company

S2M Company was first established in 1998 as a fashion retail store by the Samara brothers. They also opened a small wholesale office that imports women's clothing from china and turkey. Both brothers have extensive experience and connections in the field from working with their dad an esteemed merchant in Jordan. They opened the business with intentions of making it a family business that runs for generations. Their business bloomed and they opened several branches across Amman.

The older Samara brother involved his first born son Isam in the business early on in his life. As a young child he would go to the shops and observe how work was done. As he grew older he was given simple tasks such getting stock from the warehouse and helping a little with customers. He then took on more important tasks such as cash registry and purchasing assistant.

The Oldest Samara brother did not want his 2 elder daughters to be involved in the business and they pursued careers in graphic design. He wanted to involve his sons in the business but the youngest son was not interested. And so his older son, Isam went to college in France to study international business with the intentions to carry on the business after his father and uncle. The other Samara brother's children were young and were not in the picture.

Isam started working officially in the business in his last year of college. He didn't complete his studies for personal reasons. Isam learned from his uncles about the business but mostly he learned from the employees. Employees would give Isam great attention since he is the boss's son. However, as Isam got more mature he was able to recognize the employees' flaws. At that time, the business could not keep up with the competition due to the lack of market studies. Isam could notice that their rivals were keeping up with the changing times yet S2M kept their old ways of business. He wasn't given the authorities to apply any change to the business even though he thought that his education and young age would help the company advance in the market. The company lacked organizational structure, financial and market studies as well as a well defined future plan.

Now, Isam is the assistant CEO of the company. Isam took this role because he's gone through all the roles possible in the family company not just because he is the owner's son. He also started working in one of Jordan's largest freight companies. He took this step in getting employed in another big company to understand how big companies work. His aim is to apply all the experience he gains into his family business. From 8 am to 6 pm he works in the freight company. In the evenings and weekends he works in the family business. His uncle and dad are still involved deeply in the business. The uncle is the one who does all the purchasing for the family business. Isam and his father are responsible for everything else such as handling the finances, taxes, employees, etc.

At S2M, quarterly family meetings are conducted in order brain storm on ideas and discuss the business matters. Isam, his father and uncle along with the accountant attend these meetings. However, the final authority is for Isam's father. He is the one that makes the final decision in the end of the meetings.

Isam's future plan of the business is to sell to neighboring countries in the middle east such as Egypt, Syria and Libya. Isam plans to increase wholesale activities and become online sellers. He thinks these steps should have done a long time ago. He also plans to work on the company image to try and get into the competition as before.

Isam plans to keep the succession based on the Jordanian culture which is passing the business to his sons and daughters. However, he would recommend separating ownership from management and selecting the right non family staff to manage the business. However, Isam would like to improve the organizational structure and assign specific roles and responsibilities to everyone in the company. He is not pleased with

having three different managers at the same time. He would prefer it if each one of the top managers (his dad, uncle and himself) would specialize in a certain aspect of the business.

Case Study 5: Al Rushaid Contracting Company

Al Rushaid General Contracting has been in the business for 15 years. Mohamed Al Rushaid started his own company after extensive experience in the business. He specialized in governmental bids and quickly made a name for his company for providing good services for cheaper prices than the rest of the competition. The Al Rushaid team of experts has been in the company since it first opened. The work environment is a family atmosphere.

Mohamed wanted his 2 sons and daughter to be involved in the business. Once one of his children would graduate from college he would involve them in the business.

Unfortunately, none of the children studied in any field of the business. The daughter was the first to finish college and started working as what can be described as an administrative officer. The company had no specific structure. Roles were not specifically given to the employees. Only the architects, accountants, and engineers had specific roles. All other employees were given daily tasks that would vary depending to each project demands. After finishing college as well, the 2 sons joined the company. They were also not given certain roles but tasks.

Mohamed focused more on his eldest first born son, Yanal to be the successor that would manage the company after him. Even though Yanal did not study engineering, his

father tried teaching him everything there is about the business. Yanal needed a lot of time to understand the aspects of the business.

At first, Yanal and his siblings would struggle with every project. Their father would work with them on each project step by step. They all had to do extensive research before doing every task which was time consuming given the timeline given for the project. It was very difficult for all of them to figure out what the right thing was because all three children would feel lost.

Yanal describes getting into the business as a great challenge because he lacked the education and experience. He regrets not studying industrial engineering because it would have helped getting into the business more smoothly. However, Yanal is very enthusiastic about working in the business especially that he is aware that most of the business responsibilities lie on him.

At present, Yanal is responsible for applying to governmental bids and all the electrical shop drawings of any project. He took on this role because he has a background in Autocad software to perform the drawings.

The company is very centralized and all decisions must be made by Mohamed Rushaid the founder of the company. He takes it very personal if anything was done without consulting him first. Even if he is away on business trips, nothing goes by without his permission. Mohamed would never delegate any of his work to anyone.

Yanal's short term future plan is to take on smaller governmental bids because they are easier to win. There is not much competition in the market for small projects. Most of the contracting companies in Jordan target medium to large size projects.

In the far future, Yanal knows for a fact that he can never carry on managing the business without his dad. That is why his future plan is to change the line of business. He is not quite sure of what he wants to do, but he definitely wants to involve the family in it. He also learned from his experience, that he would advise his children to study and major in the field of whatever he changes the business to. He wants all his family members to be educated well on the line of business he moves to.

Yanal believes that family businesses should always be managed by the men of the family. And so he would pass the torch to his eldest first born son as well and so it should always be after that.

Case Study 6: Ray Architects Company

Ray architects was founded in 1982 by three brothers as a design and planning company that offers services in architecture, planning, interior designing, landscaping, and construction management.

Each brother was responsible for the parts they were experienced in. The architect was responsible for the architectural projects, the civil engineer was responsible for the civil projects and the business brother was responsible for the business structure, taxes, financials and HR.

In 1990, the company expanded into other neighboring countries and opened up branches in UAE and Palestine. Each and every branch has its own professional team of architects, engineers and administrative staff.

The eldest brother, the architect, did not want any of his children to work in the family business and thus did not encourage any of his children to study in the same field especially architecture. However, one of his daughters, Layla, had a passion of architecture and decided to pursue her degree in architecture. Her father kept his distance throughout her study so not to affect her style, vision and talent. When Layla reached her third year of university she requested to join the family business to try and apply what she's learned in college in real life. She started training in the company and observing the work. After graduation, Layla decided to work outside the family business and encouraged by her father to do so. She worked for a year and a half at a competitor company. She then resigned and decided to work for the family business. The reason behind this decision was that the family business was in a transitional stage where they were renewing their website and moving their headquarters to a new location. The new location was an old building that they renovated in one of Amman's oldest neighborhood that was very close to the downtown. Layla felt that the company needed new blood to add their views to the new changes.

Layla started working officially in the family business as an architect. She was also responsible for the social media platforms of the company. She had no office but a working-desk space just like the other employees. Employees were glad to have her aboard, but Layla felt that they were a little intimidated by the fact that she is the big boss's daughter. Layla faced a couple of challenges when she started working in the business; the first challenge was that she couldn't separate the family from the business and when conflict occurred between her father she would find it difficult to deal with it at work and act as if nothing had happened at home. Her father was very understanding of

this point and would deal with Layla in a fatherly way in both work and home. The second challenge that Layla faced was that employees would always try to deliver their thoughts and ideas to management through her. She felt pressured by this issue because she felt she was given more responsibilities than she could handle. Despite these challenges, Layla was happy to join the business especially after comparing work in a non-family business where she felt dispensable at any time given the tough economic situations in Jordan and how projects were affected. Working in her family business had given her the passion and motivation to go forward. It had reddened her of any selfish feeling that could ever come to an architect over a project and gave her a sense of team work for the greater good.

After 6 years in the family business, Layla is an architect and manager assistant. She's still responsible for the social media of the company. She is not involved in managerial decisions. Decisions are made through family meetings where the three brothers the founders of the company meet and decide on the major decisions. There isn't a succession plan for the company. However, the two other brothers' sons are planning to join the company as soon as they graduate from college. They majored in the field of the family business with the intentions to join the business. Even though there is no specific plan for who might lead the business in the future but Layla will have the seniority over her cousins since she has greater years of experience. The company has an organizational structure but roles are not specifically given with strict roles and responsibilities. This is because the company projects are usually run in a one-man-show method where the main architects run the projects and the less seniority architects would handle smaller tasks under the name of the project manager.

Layla is worried at some point in the future conflict might arise between her cousins because of different objectives. As a newly-wed, she realizes how her job is time demanding and this might be a problem when she gets kids of her own. Layla's future plans to reduce the size of work the company handles by taking small size projects so that she could handle both her business life and family life in a balanced way. She is worried though that there would be conflict with her cousins regarding this plan but she does not think about this because she believes that whatever happens in the future will be dealt with then and that there is no need for a specific plan yet.

Case Study 7: Q Printing Company

Q printing company was established in 1972 by Saeed Quqa as an advertising and printing company. Back in the 90's this field was new in Jordan and very few were specialized in. Saeed took advantage of this gap in the market and started his own business with intentions of keeping it in the family. The company specialized mainly in obituaries and parliament elections campaigns.

Early on, Saeed engaged his young boys in the business by bringing them in after school or on their holidays especially in the summer vacation to observe the work done. He would let them sit in with the graphic designers for two reasons: first, it was the "fun" part of the business; second it was the core of the business. However, Saeed never intended for his children to become designers. He only wanted them to become familiar with the work done so they can become familiar with the kind of work done when they run the business in the future.

His youngest son, Rami was always fascinated in the company and dreamed of working alongside his father once he graduated from college. The eldest was not interested in the business and pursued a career elsewhere.

Rami decided to study engineering abroad in China. His father, Saeed encouraged the idea so that his son could learn a new language that could benefit the business someday. During Rami's period of study he learned the language, customs and habits. After graduation Rami was eager to incorporate what he has learnt into the businesses. Of course his field of study would not add value to the company; however, his connections in China were valuable. And so Rami suggested starting importing the supplies used in the company directly from China instead of dealing with middlemen in Jordan. That way they could cut costs and go directly to the source. His father was thrilled by this suggestion and directly implemented his son's idea. Rami was very motivated by this support.

Rami worked hard to try and get supplies from China, learning about the trade in real life and taking the responsibility of his decisions. The biggest challenge he faced was that there was no one to teach him anything. He was on his own. He would take advice from his father but at the end of the day he had to do the work on alone away from home. At times, this huge responsibility was frustrating to Rami.

As the years passed, and as Saeed the founder of the company grew older he started to cut down the company's activities. He would not take on huge projects as before. Due to the tight economic situation, he had to cut costs by hiring few designers and an

accountant. The company was small in size and could not handle projects as before. It was getting hard to get their money from clients because no one would pay in cash.

Rami expanded the business into an import/ export business for other printing companies. He is now the assistant manager after his father. When not in China doing business, his major role is to collect money from clients.

Decisions made in the company are entirely done by Saeed the founder of the company. Rami is not involved in decisions out of respect of his father's old age and long experience. Rami only suggests his thoughts and ideas but turns to his father for the official decision.

Rami's future plan for the business when he takes over is to revive the old business and work again with big customers on big projects. However, considering the current economic situations Rami is afraid of investing more in the business. Because taking on big projects would mean hiring more people in the company plus getting new and improved equipments. They are already having difficulty collecting their money so when more money is involved from big projects it would be even harder to collect the money.

Rami also thinks that if possible he would change the line of business but keep the name as it has been in the country for over 30 years and has become very well known in the market.

Case Study 8: Swedan Company

In the 1950 Jamal Swedan was an ambitious man working in the Jordan Post Company (JPC). He had big dreams with no resources. He worked hard and put little money away from every pay check throughout the years until he had enough to partner with a small shop owner that imported food stuff from Lebanon to Jordan. He would travel with his partner to learn from him as much as he can.

In 1960, he had enough money to buy his partner out and took over the shop. But his dreams would not end there. He was inspired by the Lebanese fashion sense and started smuggling clothes from Lebanon to Jordan and opened a small clothes shop in downtown Amman – Al balad which was a dynamic market and the heart of Amman.

His business grew and there was a huge demand to his clothing. They were unique and no one was providing such clothes. He opened many branches in different locations in Jordan. Jamal wanted to keep the business in the family and so he would let all his 6 children work with him. He had 5 sons and 1 daughter. His sons were involved in purchasing, selling, inventory, cash registering, stock controlling, etc. His daughter was responsible of their public relations and dealing with suppliers. They were doing so well that Jamal believed his children did not need education but kept the option up to them.

The eldest son went to college in Lebanon; another completed his studies in London while the rest did not complete their studies upon their wishes. The 2 eldest sons were specialized in purchasing. They would travel and pick the clothing that best fit the Jordanian culture. The other children had no specific responsibilities. Their tasks were based on the daily requirements.

In 1965, Jamal decided to open Swedan center in Jabal Amman which was the elite area of Amman. He was the first to import foreign brands such as MotherCare, Deisel and Levis. The Swedan Centre was five stories high. He was also the first to start the event of a fashion show in Amman. They had to get models from Lebanon because it was frowned upon back then for Jordanian girls to model. People were amazed and the Swedan Center was a hit.

Swedan Company became an empire. In Amman they had several shops, a shopping center and a super market. Jamal then purchased a Gas station in the USA since he spent a lot of time there to purchase goods.

Jamal was the decision maker of the company. All his children would turn to him for the final decision. He had control over all the company; there was no delegation. Family members in the business did not receive fixed salaries. Each could withdraw from the accounts as much as needed. The eldest son Murad was assigned by the father as the one responsible of distributing the profits. When all his sons and daughter got married, conflict occurred between the family members. Each one had his/her own demands. At times, jealousy would spread among the family because some believed the distribution of money was not fair because it was not based on certain rules. Conflict kept getting worse over the years and the business was too much to handle. The father had a stroke and passed away. After the loss of their father, all the family members disagreed on who would be the successor to manage the entire family business. There was no plan to follow and so to resolve the conflict, the family members agreed to distribute the stores amongst them according to the Shari'a Law of Islam. Each brother took over

certain stores, the sister and mother took amount of money and some land. And so by this, their sister was out of the family business.

Each brother is trying to involve their sons in the business. However, the newer generation of the family is not enthusiastic about the business because each store is being run under the same name but in different management, the company is not getting the same profits as before. The third generation of the family believes there is no future for the business with the increased competition and brands in Jordan that have better qualities with lower prices.

The company is shriveling since some of the brothers had to close some of their stores as they can no longer profitably keep the stores open. They are struggling to keep the stores running in the market. Some of the siblings import cheap clothing from china, while others import expensive clothing from Turkey and Paris. Customers are now confused by the company because each branch of clothing store includes different types of clothes, qualities and styles.

4.2 Results

The interview participants were both founders and successors to Jordanian family businesses. From their interviews, it can be concluded that the Jordanian family businesses have no succession planning that in some cases have already or eventually would lead to conflict.

The successor interviewees have stated that the lack of corporate governance is causing problems and applying governance at the current life stage of the businesses was a hassle, messy and too complicated.

It can be seen that the lack of the proper educational background or training is holding successors back from reaching their full potential and taking the business to another level. The Al Rushaid contracting company's successors' lack of engineering background is an apparent problem. The successor cannot handle the projects and depends greatly on his founding father. This has led the successor to the future plan of changing the line of business once he becomes the manager of the company which will lead to the end of the Al Rushaid consulting company.

Also, from my observations I have concluded that the founders' control is very dominant that the successors in most cases do not have the full authority to make decisions. The successors' shadowing of founders is not preparing them well for the mature succession stage.

The results model was generated after interviewing all participants and their succession process. It includes the similar succession steps done when compared with this study's succession framework. However, only 2 case studies do not apply to the results model. The Elia Group and T&A case studies follow the study's framework and apply all stages described in [Figure 8](#).

Figure 9 - Results Succession Model

4.3 Discussion

This section provides a discussion of the case study results and their relation to the existing literature. Also this section discusses the differences and similarities of the suggested succession model and the results succession model.

The common challenges faced by Jordanian family businesses towards succession are discussed. Most of the cases show lack of succession planning, corporate governance, proper educational background, formal meetings, and good company structure.

4.3.1 The Challenges

The participants that do not have a well defined succession plan are facing similar challenges. These challenges are described below:

Lack of governance:

6 out of 8 case studies do not apply corporate governance because founders find it expensive. This goes hand in hand with Abou-el-fatouh's (2009) study on the Middle East which stated that there is a huge misconception in the Middle East on the adoption of corporate governance that it needs high costs with no guarantees on benefits. The case study is very similar to EIU-Barclays statistics that states only less than 1 in 5 families believe that corporate governance is important to the success of the business (AMCML, 2011).

The successors like in the Fashion Trends case study mention that it is messy to pick up the pieces after the founder and adopt corporate governance and will take more time, effort and resources to do so.

Elia Group adopted corporate governance when the successor officially joined the family business and they have grown since then to multiple conglomerates.

No Succession Planning

In 6 case studies, succession is dealt with as an event in the case of great illness of founder or death. Whereas, as discussed in the literature review, it needs to be dealt with as an ongoing event as performed in the T&A and Elia Group case studies. Ibrahim (1999) states that good succession planning gives family businesses the chance to select an effective leader that can revive the business.

In the Swedan case study, the company did not have a succession plan and with several siblings working together they are on the verge of downfall and might not be running for the third generation, because as Handler (1989) suggests that the absence of a succession plan could be the main reason behind the end of the family business.

The Ray Architects company's lack of succession planning might jeopardize the company as the cousins join in the business. Currently, the business is being run smoothly with no conflict. But it is highly predicted that once the big founder is out of the picture the cousins will struggle over power because there is no plan that shows who

should lead the family business; is it the founder's brother, their sons or daughter, or the big founder's daughter?

Lack of proper education or training

The educational background of the successors is not sufficient for them to manage the family business. In some of the case studies, the successors did not have the proper education to work in the family business specialization. Others lacked formal training in managerial aspects.

Most case studies show a lack of proper educational background or training in the field of business. For example, the Al Rushaid's company successor lack of engineering background might lead to the downfall of the business once he takes lead of the business.

In the Ray Architects case study, the successor has an architecture degree but while being mentored by the founder who is her father, she is being parented which makes it difficult for her to separate the family issues from the business issues. When conflict happens at work, the successor takes this conflict home and affects the family. And since the family plays a huge role in a family business, conflict might lead to unstable conditions in both business and family.

The T&A company's successor lacked the proper training in the field. He decided to work outside the company and train on different business aspects. Once he came back he applied all the things he learned from his experience into the business.

Resistance to change

Most case studies faced resistance to change from employees when the successors entered the company. In the Elia Group Company, the successor has to make an extreme decision and let go of the resistant employees in order to move forward.

In the Fashion Trends Company the employees were discontent with the change in management and having the founder's young son tell them what to do.

Another form of resistance is the founders' resistance to change. During my interviews with the founders, I noticed that the founders were very strict about their ways of management. Some are offended, as in the Al Rushaid Contracting Company, when their young successors suggest a different way of working because they feel it demeans them or that making all these changes will cost a lot with no major benefits in return.

Company Structure

All successors in case studies, except for the Elia Group, complained about the lack of structure in the family business. Most companies divide up the work based on certain tasks. Employees do not have specific clear roles and responsibilities to lead them in the business.

Al Rushaid Contracting Company demonstrate the lack of company structure where there are no specific roles but rather projects are divided into tasks and each sibling and employee does what he or she can do.

Also, in most of the case studies it can be noted that they are very centralized. Most businesses are run as a “one man show”. Starting a decentralized process is necessary for good governance by separating and delegating tasks, creating job roles and descriptions, establishing key performance indicators, and setting up measures for accountability for both employees and managers. This problem comes in line with the problem in Agency theory presented by La Porta, Lopez de Silanes & Shleifer (1999) that family businesses are distinctively inclined to internal dysfunction mostly because of the autonomy of the owners’ (in that case the agents) control in the process of decision making.

4.3.2 Succession Planning and the Family Protocol

When it comes to the selection of successors, the Jordanian culture still adheres to the masculine management stereotype and the perceived success of family owned businesses is greatly impacted by gender. This has nothing to do with gender equality, but rather because the male family members are the ones that carry on the family name. As Fahed-Sreih (2006) describes that in the Middle East family businesses are considered to enhance the family name and thus enhance the family standing. That is why founders focus mainly on their first-born sons.

Companies that have a succession plan increase their value by making sure the most talented family member becomes a successor. Otherwise, Aranoff, Mclure and Ward (2003) the integrity of the business will be ruined.

The important question here is why don't founders of Jordanian family businesses consider succession planning? As discussed in the literature review, succession in Jordan usually occurs as a onetime event when the founder is greatly ill or dead. That is why founder are afraid to think of the future. Morris et al (1996) propose main areas that must be addressed in succession planning which are: the preparation of heirs, the relationship between the family and business members, planning actions.

Jordanian family businesses need to have a succession plan to avoid conflict once the founder no longer leads the business.

In the Elia Group case study, they established a family protocol that includes policies of the family business that has protected them so far from any conflict. Their family protocol outlines the core mission and vision of the company, and the roles and responsibilities of every governance body. Moreover, the family protocol specifies how each member of the family can get involved in the business. Establishing a family protocol helped the Elia Group Company to predict and prevent misunderstandings or conflict among family members as well as propagate the vision of the business to coming generations. A good requirement to add to a family policy is to make family members work outside the family business for a specified period of time to gain better experience and gain valuable skills that they can bring to the family business. Another requirement would be to set education standards for family members that intend to join the company along with specified salaries.

Finally, Lansberg (1988) states that in order for a succession process to be successful, founders of family businesses need to know the difference between mentoring and

parenting. It is important to find just the right balance between mentoring and parenting. Ray Architects founder was parenting his daughter who is being mentored as for succession but the parenting style confused the successor and she couldn't separate the conflict and issues of work from family.

In order for family businesses avoid resistance to succession planning, a necessary step is to keep the employees informed with the business plans regarding corporate governance and succession in order to try and limit resistance to succession planning.

4.3.3 Succession Theoretical Models

The interview results show that family play a major role in the family business and so Walsh's (2011) Altered Three Circle Model best describes the Jordanian family owned businesses (see [Figure 2](#) in the [Literature Review](#) chapter). From the interviews, it can be concluded that the family circle is very dominant and needs special attention to ensure the family business is run smoothly.

According to the Systems theory, the overlap among the three sub-systems (family, ownership and business) may lead to conflict due to the different perspectives held within each family business actor on issues related. In such situations of conflict, a family meeting, assembly or council could act as a platform that fosters interaction to enable the system participants to work through their conflicts and come up with mutual solutions that meet both the individual and business needs (Marion & Uhl-Bien, 2001). Moreover, by having a common agreement in such interactions may result to a dynamic stability that lies under the arbitrariness of the composite systems.

Also, in most of the case studies it can be noted that they are very centralized. Most businesses are run as a “one man show”. Starting a decentralized process is necessary for good governance by separating and delegating tasks, creating job roles and descriptions, establishing key performance indicators, and setting up measures for accountability for both employees and managers. This problem comes in line with the problem in Agency theory presented by La Porta, Lopez de Silanes & Shleifer (1999) that family businesses are distinctively inclined to internal dysfunction mostly because of the autonomy of the owners’ (in that case the agents) control in the process of decision making.

A good succession plan is important because based on the Agency theory, over the course of generations the weakness of family ties and problems of opportunism increases (Blanco-Mazagatos V, de Quevedo-Puente E, & Castrillo L A, 2007). And so members of the family can manage the business and benefit of expensive salaries or sometimes make decisions to their own interest which is unacceptable to the interest of the business. That is why having the right people at the right position at the right time all play a major role in good succession practice.

4.3.4 The Need for Corporate Governance

It might be true that applying CG is expensive because family businesses would need to restructure the company, hire independent directors and do external audits. But in the long term, the benefits of CG outweigh these costs. For example in the T&A case study, they were aware that in order to reach their plan of buying out one of their franchises and invest in other ventures they had to apply corporate governance. They are trying

their best to implement an excellent framework so that investors would be more confident in investing in their family business. And this is one of the most important benefits of corporate governance. By applying corporate governance to family businesses, investors would be encouraged to invest and thus the business could either venture into new markets or they could internationalize the business and go global.

To develop the family corporate governance, companies need to include the following elements proposed by Mahmood S (2008): board of directors, financial reporting, and internal and external audits.

This research proves that good corporate governance helps the continuity of the family business. 2 out of 8 (T&A company and Elia Company) case studies apply corporate governance and have shown greater company growth and prospects than the others that do not have CG. Mahmood S (2008) shows that good corporate governance helps family businesses achieve their corporate goals efficiently and thus continue on across generations.

A close look at the case studies, founders seem to be reluctant to giving up control and comply with requirements of governance and transparency. In the Jordanian culture, many business founders hesitate to disclose financial results because they fear of the envious eyes of the competition or some family members, and because they fear to attract outside investors that could make them lose their control over the family. However, an annual report of the family business financial outputs could act as a communication tool that unifies family members because family members own for both financial and non-financial reasons (Evans F & DeKreek S, nd).

4.3.5 The Board

In Jordan, small to medium sized companies are dominating the private sectors, and so are all 8 case studies discussed. In these case studies it can be seen that the roles and relationships among the family itself, board directors, shareholders and the management of the businesses are inclined to be overlapping and ambiguous. That is why the very first step for family owned businesses to implement good CG practices is to start distinctions between all those entities; and as discussed in the literature review chapter the best place to start this is with an effectual board of directors.

In most of the case studies, there is a board but it is running in an ad hoc manner and not very formal. Even though this informality has its advantages such as being more flexible and responsive, however, as the family-owned business grows it could be unsustainable (Jordaan, 2012).

During the interviews, founders showed some fear of the idea of a strong board because it might affect their power. Especially in the Jordanian culture, the founders who are obviously the elders of the family need to have the final say without interference from anyone. A good solution to this would be having an advisory committee in order to compliment the company's board. This council could provide advice to the board without affecting the governance of the company or power structure.

The board needs to have specific tasks such as appointing the company goals, setting management responsibilities, agreeing to important new ventures, meeting regularly to complete their jobs.

4.3.6 Theoretical Succession Framework in Comparison with Results Model

Comparing the theoretical succession model (see [Figure 8](#)) in this research and the results succession model (see [Figure 9](#)), it can be noted that the results model includes less stages than the suggested succession model.

The results succession model conforms with the succession processes explained in literature (Stavrou, 1999; Poutziouris and Chittenden, 1996; Handler, 1989):

1. Preparation of offspring early in life and before joining the business;
2. Integration of offspring into the business in several roles;
3. Assuming the leadership role in the business.

However, the case studies show that these steps are not enough. To have an effective succession plan, Jordanian family businesses need to apply Longenecker et al (2006) framework. The results model needs to include the following additional stages to match the theoretical succession framework:

- The pre-business stage: No formal planning. The potential heir needs to become familiar with the business at an early stage. This stage is different from the introductory stage in that parents start introducing their children to certain people within the business and become associated to the business itself. This stage is a good start for implanting the passion for running the family business just like the Elia case study where the founder would point out to his desk at the back of the store and tell his son that one day all this would be his.
- The advanced functional stage: once the successor has gone through the functional stage which is where he/ she starts working full time in the company

and goes through different non-managerial positions, they need to then assume all managerial positions before becoming the president or general manager of the family business.

Chapter 5 CONCLUSIONS, IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Succession is inevitable in any family business. And so succession planning is an important part of doing business in FOBs. Succession planning is no longer about management change; it is also about helping define the business strategies into business goals in order to ensure the continuity of the company to generations.

This research is designed to study succession planning in family businesses in Jordan along with their problems, causes, consequences and remedies. The study ventures into untouched grounds, given that succession in family businesses in Jordanian culture is scarce or non-existent.

In order to achieve its proposed objectives, the research examines 8 case studies of family owned businesses from different sectors in their second generation. The case studies show that most of the family businesses do not adopt governance structure.

Founders tend to refuse to adopt corporate governance because of its high costs and relatively unsure benefits. Successors on the other hand are unable to adopt corporate governance because applying it at a later stage in life of the business makes it too messy and difficult.

Jordanian family business founders are usually too afraid to plan for the succession future of their company because that would assume their illness or death. Moreover, founders are very emotionally attached to their business that imagining letting go of the management is almost impossible. However, parents need to plan ahead to ensure their business moves on to generations without conflict.

Jordanian family businesses adhere to the tradition of masculine management stereotype because male family members are the one that carry out the name of the family.

Successors seem to lack the proper educational background or training background, especially training outside the company. Training outside the company is important to get further insight on how work can be done.

The major problems faced by family businesses in Jordan were because of the lack of succession planning. Family feuds, resistance to change, conflict of interests, unsuitable successors, lack of skills and talent in coming generations, to name a few were part of the problems faced. However, the most important factor that is holding successors from continuing the journey of their predecessors is the founders' emotional attachment to the business which makes it difficult for the successor to assume a leadership role in the business if the offspring stays under the wing of the founding father of the company.

Succession needs to be an ongoing event not just an event that occurs when the founder of the company dies or get ill. A succession plan needs to be in place to set the vision, goals, governance, standards, successor selection, family protocol, and succession process.

The suggested succession framework that family businesses in Jordan need to follow are concluded in the following stages: pre-business stage, introductory stage, introductory functional stage, functional stage, advanced functional stage, early succession stage and finally mature succession stage.

Families in Jordan are very proud of their family names and legacy that they always nominate a family member to be the successor and particularly their first male born sons.

This research showed that Walsh's altered three circle model best describes the relationships between the three circles than the three circle model. The altered model emphasizes that family is very important to the family business.

Applying corporate governance at a later stage in the family business could be hard to do as the successors can find it messy to pick up after their predecessors as I have noticed from the case studies discussed in this research. And so I have concluded that applying corporate governance at the right time in the family business life stage can strengthen the family ties, bring stability to the operations of the business, bestow further for effective management, and help employ management talent. Also applying corporate governance at the appropriate time of the business life cycle helps avoid conflicts that arise throughout the entire life of the business. It opens up communication among the members that allows family members to discuss issues related to the business.

The following list includes the most important points that need to be considered when creating a succession plan:

- The goals associated to the succession
- The criteria for selecting a successor
- The steps for successor preparation
- The needed training for successors

It is recommended for Jordanian family businesses to follow the succession process described by Longenecker J. et al (2006) that includes 7 important stages:

- I. The pre-business stage in which the potential successors becomes familiar with the family business early with no formal training. For example the successor can only visit the work place and sit around and observe.
- II. The introductory stage in which the successor gets more training and is introduced to the business and certain important individuals indirectly. For example the successor could get introduced to the accountant, managing director or designer of the company and observe certain tasks.
- III. The introductory stage in which the successor begins working as a part-time employee and becomes involved in various functional areas as time passes by. For example, the successor could work part-time in their summer vacation as a sales executive or clerk. At this stage it is important to let potential successors to train at other companies as well.
- IV. The functional stage in which the successor formally works full time at the company. For example, the successor joins the business after graduating from college and assigned a full time job role.
- V. The advanced functional stage in which the successor takes on a managerial position that allows him/ her to direct the work but not actually manage the business.
- VI. The early succession stage in which the successor becomes the general manager and exercises the overall direction of business. However, at this stage the parent is still involved in the background.

VII. The mature succession stage in which the transition of power is complete and the successor becomes the leader of the business.

I highly recommend for successor in their third stage of the succession process (introductory functional) to work for other companies in order to gain a different perspective of how things can be done differently. That way the successor can fuse different work styles from his/ her experience.

One of the major challenges in Jordanian family businesses is that founders seem to be unwilling to giving up boardroom control and comply with the requirements of transparency and governance. A board of directors is a main element of developing a code of corporate governance.

Having a board of directors is very important for family businesses. The founder can hire trusted friends or consultants from different backgrounds. Founders also need to have an open mind for their successors' ideas and stop casting their shadows over their children, allowing them to grow on their own but still under their management so once the successor takes over the business he/ she is well prepared.

Family businesses need to have a good company structure where each person in the company has a set of roles and responsibilities. Also, each family business needs to set its goals, values, vision and culture that is conveyed to all employees and successors to take over the business. This will ensure the continuity of the family business with all its unique characteristics and successors won't feel lost.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Interview participants were reluctant not very open on succession conflicts and issues because they wanted to reflect a good image of their business even though they were aware that their name would be anonymous in the study and that this research is to help other family businesses.

Future research would include the role of women nowadays. Most family businesses disregard women and opt for their first born sons to be successors.

Also, the researcher would like to follow up on the participating companies and see their succession development into the third generation.

APPENDIX 1

Qualitative Interview Schedule

Letter of introduction

Dear Business Owners/ Managers

My name is Furat Jabr and I am a student with the University of Liverpool. I am undertaking my dissertation that leads to the production of research on the topic of succession planning in family owned businesses in Jordan. The main purpose of my research is to learn about the problems, causes, consequences and remedies of succession planning in family owned businesses in Jordan.

I would be appreciative if you could volunteer to assist me in my research by taking part in an interview that covers certain aspects of the topic in research. The questions are enclosed and will take about 40 minutes of your time.

The information resulting from the interview will be very helpful for family businesses to succeed from one generation to the next. This information might be used in classrooms for instructing students in universities or other organizations around the world. Hopefully, the information resulting from the interviews is useful to enhance the succession planning among family owned business.

In the following pages, you will be asked question concerning your business and your succession process.

Please be assured that all information given will be treated in extreme and strict confidence. The name of your company will not be released publicly and no individual respondent shall be identified to any party or written publication.

If you have inquiries regarding this research you can contact me by email furat.jabr@gmail.com or phone 00962795729998. If you wish, you can keep a copy of the interview questions.

Thank you for your assistance

Yours sincerely,

Furat Jabr

Predecessor Interview

Category: Avoiding uncertainty

This will help me assess to what extent family members of the business strive to avoid uncertainty by depending on norms, bureaucratic practices to try and ease the volatility of future events.

1. Is there a well defined management transition plan? Please explain.
2. Is there a family committee or board? If yes, do you meet regularly to discuss the role of each family member, the growth of business? Do you think it is effective?
3. Do you perform regular analysis concerning the future of the family and the business in the family business? Please explain.
4. Are family members that work in the business treated the same way as the non-family employees? Please explain.

Category: Future orientation

1. Is there a clear set of policies that define how family members need to be introduced to the business? (Is there any special training, positions assumed, or any kind of preparation required?)
2. Is there a written succession plan to make sure that the business can survive if a key player in the family business is lost?
3. Is there a certain system in place to train future successors? For example do they need to go get some experience in the industry first outside the business, or do they have to go to college?
4. Is there a set of rules that manage how family members are hired? Please explain.

Successor Interview:

Category: History in the Business

1. What is your first memory of the business from your childhood? Are there any particular events?
2. When did you start to engage in the business? How? Any specific tasks?
3. On whose initiative did you engage in the business?
4. How did you learn about the business? And by whom?
5. Why did you decide to work for the business? When was this decided and by whom?
6. Any considerations or alternatives?
7. How was your experience getting into the business? Who helped you?
8. What reactions did you receive from the other family members, employees, suppliers and customers when you first started?
9. What roles did you take so far? If many changes, why did you go through so many changes?
10. Did you encounter any problems? Please explain. If yes, what were your solutions?
11. Did conflict occur? If yes, by whom and about what? How were such conflicts dealt with?
12. What do you like most or consider most fun in the business?

Category: Current role of successor in business

1. What is your role now? Please explain (why did you take this role, and how long have you been in this role?)
2. What are your daily tasks?
3. Are you involved in managerial decisions? If yes, who else other than you?
4. How do you work exactly: through council, board meetings, etc?
5. How exactly are decisions made? By whom?
6. Are you an owner of the business? What is the ownership structure?

Category: Future role of successor in business

1. What are your future envisions of the business? (What are your plans and who will be involved?)
2. How do you work on the succession process?
3. What is decided for the future? Do you want this to happen? If not, how would you want it to be?
4. What are your thoughts about the current succession process?
5. Who is driving the succession process?
6. Do you believe someone (or something) is holding you back in the business?
7. How will your role change in the business?
8. Will there be any other roles that need to be changed?
9. What do you think must remain the same after succession? Please explain why and how.
10. Do you like to change anything? Please explain why, how and when.
11. Do you foresee any future challenges or difficulties to the changes?

APPENDIX 2

Verbatim Interview Transcript Sample

Elia Group: Successor interview

The interview below was conducted with the acting Chairman of the Elia Group in his office over a cup of coffee who happens to be the successor of the company. The interview in his office allowed me to not only do a one on one interview but also observe the GM in his workplace as well. The synopsis of the interview is shown below:

Interviewer: Hello Mr. Edward. As you know I am conducting my dissertation research on the succession planning in family businesses in Jordan. I want to highlight the problems, consequences and remedies of succession since only 3% of businesses survive to the third generation; a shocking statistic that obviously needs paying attention to. Your participation will help this study come up with results that will help companies succeed from one generation to the next and enhance their succession planning. This interview is divided into three sections: your history in the business, your current role in the business and your future role in the business.

Interviewee: Sounds good [smiling].

Interviewer: Ok, then let's start with the first section of the interview. What is your first memory of the business from your childhood? Are there any particular events?

Interviewee: The first thing I remember when I was a little boy my father would bring me to his shop (back then we started small and my father had a shop in downtown Amman) and point to his desk at the back of the office and tell: “Son, one day all this will be yours!” I was very intrigued by the idea of owning a managing an entire store. My father planted his dream and it became my dream as well.

Interviewer: When did you start to engage in the business? How? Any specific tasks?

Interviewee: in the 70's I started working with my father as a part-time job. I would work on the machines in the factory and learn every aspect of the operations. I was the first to be in and the last to leave. I would wear the overalls and work hard because I was eager and passionate about the business. And I knew back then how important it was to know the operations of the machines for my future in the business.

Interviewer: On whose initiative did you did you engage in the business?

Interviewee: My dad's. He was the one to tell me to start working part-time.

Interviewer: How did you learn about the business? And by whom?

Interviewee: My dad taught me a lot and by first-hand experience at the factory. The employees would treat me as an employee and give me instructions on how to work. I also would do some research of my own by studying on certain subjects and lead by example.

Interviewer: Why did you decide to work for the business? When was this decided and by whom?

Interviewee: Looking back, the idea of working in the business was always implanted indirectly in my head. But now I realize it was planned by my father for me to carry on his business and to my children and so on. And so I can say I became passionate about the business. My father's enthusiasm and passion was very inspiring to me. Another thing, was seeing the business grow over the years made me even more eager to work for the business and be involved in this growth for both work and the family.

Interviewer: Any considerations or alternatives?

Interviewee: No, I always wanted to work for the family business. I realized when I was school that I was privileged to have a family business that can work in when I graduate unlike my colleagues who would always worry of their future and where would they want to start their career once they graduate. This realization made me determent to work for the family business and nowhere else. I was also the main focus of my father for being his successor being his first born son.

Interviewer: How was your experience getting into the business? Who helped you?

Interviewee: My experience was very beneficial. Starting at an early age as a part time employee in the factory helped me learn the back-end of our business. With my father's help and the employees' I was able to operate machines. I didn't want to be holding a managerial position just because I was the owner's son. I wanted to get the position because I deserved it not because I inherited it. I wanted to earn the respect of working my way through.

Interviewer: What reactions did you get from family members, employees, suppliers and customers when you first started?

Interviewee: family members were very encouraging because they saw in me the continuity of the business because I was serious about working in the business early on in my life. My commitment showed the employees that I was not a spoiled little boy which earned me the respect. I did not deal with customers or suppliers back then because I was focusing on working in the factory at first.

Interviewer: What roles did you take so far? If many changes, why did you go through so many changes?

Interviewee: I took on several roles at the factory. Every time I would learn the operation of a certain machine until I could count every machine, the number of output it generated. For example I could count every tissue in each tissue box we generated. I took all sorts of job roles because I wanted to every aspect of the business.

Interviewer: Did you encounter any problems? Please explain. If yes, what were your solutions?

Interviewee: when I graduated from college with an engineering degree, I started implementing the things I've learnt in school. I did so many changes and my father encouraged it. The older employees were not happy with the changes. I documented every single operation, machine, procedure so cut the time costs of training employees and save time on all the questions and answers. I had to do drastic changes to the operations. I even bought in new advanced machinery. The employees resisted all these changes and would give attitudes at work. I strongly believed we had to bring in new blood. I wouldn't settle for being mediocre. We had to let go of the old employees and bring in new more educated employees.

Interviewer: Did conflict occur? If yes, by whom and about what? How were such conflicts dealt with?

Interviewee: The only conflict was with the employees who resisted change and we dealt with that by getting new blood in the company. In the family there were no conflict only encouragement. In fact, the family believed in me so much that I felt pressured. They thought I knew the solution for every problem because I was the well educated well trained member of the family.

Interviewer: What do you like most or consider most fun in the business?

Interviewee: The fact of running and managing the business was the most fun. Having to implement my ideas was a fun challenge that I took on myself.

Interviewer: Ok now we will be talking about your current role in the business. What is your role now? Please explain (why did you take this role, and how long have you been in this role?)

Interviewee: I am the Vice Chairman – acting chairman of the Elia Group. I've recently been the acting Chairman due to my father's illness but been the vice chairman since we separated the management from ownership in 2004.

Interviewer: What are your daily tasks?

Interviewee: My daily tasks include strategy, top level HR activities, important legal issues, expansion studies, PR issues, CSR issues and partners.

Interviewer: Are you involved in managerial decisions? If yes, who else other than you?

Interviewee: We have an authority's matrix. Decisions are made according to shares owners, board directors.

Interviewer: How do you work exactly?

Interviewee: We work through our national councils depending on authority.

Interviewer: How exactly are decisions made? By whom?

Interviewee: decisions are made according to the decision matrix but the big decisions such as investing in new ventures goes through the board of directors and final decision is up to me.

Interviewer: Are you an owner of the business? What is the ownership structure?

Interviewee: The Company is a family holding. It is divided into two parts: the core business, and other investments.

Interviewer: Very well. We are almost done with the interview. We have reached the final part of the interview which goes through your future role as a successor in the business. What are your future envisions of the business?

Interviewee: I would like for our core business to be the number one in every product category in the MENA region and to walk away from running the other small investments we have by completely delegating the management to others.

Interviewer: How do you work on the succession process?

Interviewee: We always update the family protocol to govern family members.

Interviewer: What are your thoughts about the current succession process?

Interviewee: I think it is good enough to prepare and select successors. Our family has grown since the family business was first established and so our succession process ensure that only the best fit family member can be the successors. The family protocol helps select several qualified successors based on set criteria.

Interviewer: How will your role change in the business?

Interviewee: I want to empower non family members more and move away from the daily decision making.

Interviewer: Will there be any roles that need to be changed?

Interviewee: As far as I know, no. However, if any changes need to be made in the future we are always trying to be flexible enough to make necessary changes.

Interviewer: What do you think must remain the same after succession? Please explain why and when?

Interviewee: After succession, our line of business, goals, vision, culture and values must remain. They are what set us apart from the rest of the market.

Interviewer: Do you like to change anything? Please explain why, how and when?

Interviewee: To be honest, no. maybe because I was seriously involved in the business at an early age and got to plan our set goals and objectives that we continually seek to fulfill that I do not want to change anything specific. But I do always strive to accomplish our future objectives concerning both the family and business.

Interviewer: Do you foresee any future challenges or difficulties to the changes?

Interviewee: Always. I am afraid that the future generations would go astray our values, culture and goals.

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